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AI Policy in Blended Intensive Programmes (BIPs) in Europe: Insights from ENHANCE Alliance

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Abstract

The increased integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into hybrid mobility within the ENHANCE Alliance in Europe raises a number of pedagogical, organisational, and regulatory questions. This chapter examines the AI policy in Blended Intensive Programmes (BIPs), by analysing its implementation, such as AI administrative chatbots, AI-supported collaboration in group tasks, AI as a reflective teammate, and LLM-enabled co-creation. The study adopts a qualitative, document-based analysis supported by institutional evidence and the EU legal frameworks, particularly the AI Act and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Additionally, UNESCO's Guidance for Generative AI in Education and Research provides a global perspective. Our findings reveal that the discussed AI cases require careful alignment with the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and human-centred (international and institutional) governance to ensure responsible and inclusive educational innovation in BIPs.

Keywords: AI policy, Blended Intensive Programmes (BIPs), ENHANCE Alliance, Human-AI Interaction (HAI), hybrid mobility, collaboration, reflective learning, co-creation

1. Introduction

Student mobility in Europe has progressively evolved from a geographically anchored model towards hybrid participation, digital collaboration, and multilingual inclusion (European Students' Union, 2019; Kavasakalis & Gkiza, 2022; Antal-Berbecaru et al., 2024). Erasmus+ and similar European initiatives have intended to formalise collaboration beyond just bilateral exchange (European Commission, 2025), especially after the Lisbon Recognition Convention and the Bologna Process, which laid foundations of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) through the introduction of common degree structures, credit systems, and recognition procedures (Council of Europe & UNESCO, 1997; Eurydice, 2025). It made the European higher education system more embedded in global knowledge economies, with a conceptual shift from mobility-as-movement to mobility-as-participation (Knight, 2019; Veletsianos & Houlden, 2019).

The ENHANCE Alliance, founded in 2019, is one of the European Commission's agreements, which brought together ten universities of technology (all of them focusing on engineering, sustainability and innovation) to pursue an integrated European campus via multilingual learning and intercultural collaboration (ENHANCE Alliance, 2019; 2024; European Commission; 2024, March 26; European Parliament Research Service, 2025). It includes approximately 293,000 students and 63,000 employees, which increases both opportunities and risks of educational technology and generative AI in Blended Intensive Programmes or BIPs (Polyakova et al. 2024; Polyakova, 2024). BIPs, formalised under Erasmus+ 2021–2027, combine a short physical mobility period with a virtual component that is flexible in duration and design, and enable universities to compress the in-person phase by teaching the rest of the syllabus through online collaboration (European Commission, 2025; CIVIS Alliance, 2026). This structure is important for AI policy because it shifts its pedagogical value toward the virtual phase, in which the in-person period is short; therefore, the effectiveness of a BIP preparatory stage, shared framing, and multilingual coordination becomes decisive (O'Dowd, 2021; SEPIE, 2022; Cress & Kimmerle, 2023; OECD, 2026).

Likewise, the ENHANCE Alliance's strategy is often understood through the axes of Innovative Organisation, Future Knowledge, and One Campus (ENHANCE Alliance, 2023). This structure offers a multi-layered context in which AI can be integrated not merely as a tool but also as a sociotechnical teammate across institutional systems, languages, and cultures (European University Association, 2026; CIVIS Alliance, 2026). On the one hand, the AI component transforms alliances into powerful innovation platforms; on the other hand, it intensifies challenges related to interoperability, equal opportunities, and alignment with competence-oriented training in the European education systems (Polyakova & Gaslyan-Sargsyan, 2019). AI has been increasingly giving a response to such constraints in mobility as language barriers, time-zone asynchrony, access to institutional information, and difficulties in coordinating student teams in compressed timeframes (Nguyen et al., 2024; Li et al., 2025). In this context, conversational systems and LLM-based tools can help students work across languages, provide quick feedback, and support collaboration in challenge-based environments, including those related to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, SDGs (Leal Filho et al., 2024; Aditya, 2026).

Furthermore, the integration of AI in the EU higher education goes beyond purely pedagogical dimensions. It is governed by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which structures lawful data minimisation, transparency, and accountability (European Union, 2016), together with

the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act), which establishes risk-based obligations that include transparency and human oversight for certain educational contexts (European Union, 2024). The AI Act's timeline has accelerated institutional work across 2025 and 2026, as early provisions came into practice in 2025 while its full implementation approaches around 2026 (European Union, 2024; European Commission, 2025). In parallel, global policy has framed generative AI in education demanding AI skills development among students, teachers, and administrative staff (UNESCO, 2023; OECD, 2023; OECD, 2026).

2. Background

Today, Human-AI interaction is often understood as cognitive, social, and cultural processes through which students interact with AI systems as teammates (Zheng et al., 2025). Early research in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) focused mainly on usability and interface design (Norman, 2013). However, recent Human-AI interaction (HAI) studies show that AI systems can influence how users think, perceive, and behave (Kaate et al., 2025). In this context, the media equation (Reeves & Nass, 1996) and the social presence theory (Short et al., 1976) suggest that people may assign social qualities to computer systems, which can affect their trust in them and their reliance on them (Biocca et al., 2003; Larchen, 2020; Klein, 2025). Similarly, research on trust calibration in automation highlights the importance of appropriate transparency when people interact with intelligent systems (Mitchell, 2025), including the participants of the ENHANCE Alliance.

Beyond cognitive and usability perspectives, sociocultural theories offer other ways to understand the AI use in higher education and in BIPs collaboration. Distributed cognition (Hutchins, 1995) explains knowledge as something that develops through interaction among people, tools, and environments. Similarly, sociometrical approaches point out that human actions and technologies are closely connected and shape practices together (Bayne, 2015; Antal-Berbecaru et al., 2024). More research argues that technologies are not just tools that support work and learning, but active team players that aid organisational and educational processes (Maack, 2024; Romero, 2025). These ideas support current views on AI as part of networks that include both human and nonhuman teammates. They connect with relational and posthuman approaches in educational technology (Wang & Wang, 2025) where hybrid intelligence emerges as a result of joint human and AI capabilities (Kong et al., 2025).

Multilingual and multicultural contexts, in this regard, introduce further complexity in the use of language technologies such as machine translation, automated transcription, and large language models (LLMs). They mediate communication across linguistic boundaries and influence epistemic authority, participation, and inclusion (Sangkawong, 2025; Chan, 2025) among the BIP exchange participants. Cultural dimensions such as distance, individualism versus collectivism, and uncertainty shape how users interpret technological authority and risk (Komatsu et al, 2026). Studies in intercultural communication suggest that rights and rules surrounding collaboration and academic integrity vary across cultures (Hall, 1976; Wang, 2025; Cannavale, 2025), which may influence how BIP students perceive AI-generated content and co-authorship with intelligent systems. Meanwhile, international policy frameworks shape how artificial intelligence can be integrated into education. Among them, UNESCO's Guidance for Generative AI in Education and Research provides a global legal perspective (UNESCO, 2023) through a human-centred approach, emphasizing on the aspect that artificial intelligence should enhance and not narrow human capabilities.

Students from the ENHANCE Alliance are an important target group to study these issues. They come from different universities, language backgrounds, and fields of study. Because of this diversity, they need to develop not only technical skills but also AI literacy, ethical awareness, and the ability to work well with others (Pan et al., 2025), especially in multicultural and multilingual contexts (Larchen Costuchen et al., 2025). In hybrid and virtual projects, which reflect wider changes in global work structures (Swartz et al., 2025), students perform in teams, communicate asynchronously, and use AI-supported tools in their workflows. Theories of computer-supported cooperative work (CSCW) and sociotechnical systems help to explain how this shared knowledge and collective intelligence develop through interaction between humans and the AI systems (Al-Abdullatif, 2025).

3. Main focus of the chapter

The main objective of this chapter is to analyse AI policy in the ENHANCE mobility context through four practical cases that address the following use of AI in Blended Intensive Programmes (BIPs): AI chatbots for administrative guidance (AI Use 1), AI-support in collaborative tasks (AI Use 2), AI as a reflective teammate (AI Use 3), and LLM-supported co-creation in the virtual phase (AI Use 4).

In relation to AI Use 1, BIP formats require formal documentation, recognition of learning outcomes, and close cooperation between the partner institutions. As student mobility involves cross-border data exchange (European Parliament & Council, 2016), the integration of AI tools must comply with the General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR (European Data Protection Board, 2020; 2024) and, increasingly, the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (European Parliament & Council, 2024). The AI use in BIPs is therefore both a pedagogical and a regulatory matter (Smuha, 2021; Veale & Borgesius, 2021) because administrative chatbots can improve access to information in multilingual and multicultural mobility settings and provide real-time guidance. However, they may process personal data, which requires identification of controller responsibilities. This component needs the lawful basis to ensure transparency and appropriate safeguards under the GDPR (European Data Protection Board, 2020; 2024). While typically it is not high-risk under the AI Act when such chatbots are limited to information provision, their classification may change if they influence eligibility or administrative decisions.

Regarding AI Use 2, AI-supported challenge-based collaboration provides the core model of intercultural teamwork in BIPs. AI tools can support coordination and knowledge creation (Järvelä et al., 2023; Ouyang et al., 2023), but they may also shape evaluation and participation (Usher, 2025.; AlGhamdi et al., 2026). If the AI outputs influence grading or significant academic decisions, GDPR provisions on profiling and automated decision-making become relevant, and high-risk classification under the AI Act may arise (European Data Protection Board, 2020; 2024). Legal risk thus depends on how the tool is functionally integrated into assessment in BIPs (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2024).

With respect to AI Use 3, reflective AI teammates support metacognition and intercultural learning (Auer, 2025), yet reflective content may include sensitive personal data (European Data Protection Board, 2020; 2024). This triggers strict data protection safeguards and careful consideration of legal bases, especially where reflection is linked to credit recognition. If AI-

generated feedback affects grading, requirements concerning fairness, transparency, and human oversight become central (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2024).

Finally, in correspondence with AI Use 4, which covers LLM-supported co-creation in the virtual phase, it transforms the online component of BIPs into space for active knowledge production (Maier et al., 2025). At the same time, generative AI raises questions about data transfer, authorship, and accountability. Under the AI Act, universities act as deployers of general-purpose AI systems and must ensure transparency and effective human supervision, particularly in task assessment (European Parliament & Council, 2024).

4. Method and data synthesis

This study uses a qualitative, document-based analysis to examine four AI-enabled BIP functions, from AI Use 1 to AI Use 4 (Table 1). The empirical base combines the ENHANCE Alliance documentation and the BIP-related institutional data (ENHANCE Alliance, 2023). As some BIP details are not publicly described (e.g., specific tools, datasets, or data retention policies), our analysis relies on open data, allowing readers to verify and replicate findings.

To explore BIP chatbot regulation, this chapter uses materials from RWTH Aachen University describing their data protection framework for chatbot services and the implementation of an institutionally managed LLM system (RWTH Aachen University, 2024a, July 16; RWTH Aachen University, 2024b, December 11; RWTH Aachen University IT Center, n.d.). We also consider guidance from KTH Royal Institute of Technology on the use of generative AI in teaching contexts (KTH Royal Institute of Technology, 2026, January 8; January 28). In addition, this report draws cross-alliance pedagogical evidence from a documented BIP on science communication and generative AI delivered by the Arqus Alliance (Arqus Alliance, 2025, May 15).

At the European level, the AI Act (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2024) plays an important role in protecting democratic values while UNESCO's (2023) Guidance for Generative AI in Education and Research provides a global perspective. The legal analysis follows a doctrinal approach and focuses on the main principles of the GDPR (European Data Protection Board, 2020; 2024). It also examines the situations that require stronger obligations, especially when a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) is required under Article 35, as well as the risk-based framework and implementation timeline of the AI Act (European Union, 2016; 2024).

Because DPIAs are often used as internal compliance tools and are not always publicly available, this study compares the GDPR threshold in Article 35 with official guidance from EU institutions and regulators (Regulation EU 2016/679, Article 35). The analysis includes explanations from the European Commission on when a DPIA is required and guidance from the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) on AI-related data protection and DPIA practices (European Commission, 2024; European Data Protection Board, 2024).

We organised our findings into a comparative matrix (Table 1) that summarises the data and links each AI case to legal obligations in the BIP context.

Table 1. Synthesis of AI-enabled BIP functions

Governance Dimension	AI Use 1: Administrative Chatbot	AI Use 2: AI-Supported Collaboration	AI Use 3: Reflective AI Teammate	AI Use 4: LLM Co-Creation in the Virtual Phase
Primary Function	Multilingual onboarding and administrative guidance	Team coordination, idea generation, collaborative synthesis	Metacognitive scaffolding and formative feedback	Collaborative writing, design and knowledge production
Pedagogical Role	Reduces administrative burden; gives indirect support for mobility learning	Supports intercultural teamwork and hybrid intelligence	Enhances reflection and intercultural learning	Transforms the virtual phase into active collaborative learning
Legal Basis (GDPR)	Art. 6(1)(e) Public task	Art. 6(1)(e); possibly 6(1)(f) for analytics	Art. 6(1)(e); Art. 9 if sensitive data is disclosed	Art. 6(1)(e); additional lawful basis if personal data is included in prompts
Key GDPR Risks	Transparency; data minimisation; cross-border transfers	Profiling; monitoring; automated decision-making	Sensitive personal data processing	International transfers; reuse of prompts; authorship accountability
Article 22 Risk	Low unless when influences eligibility	Moderate-High if it influences grading	Moderate if AI feedback affects assessment	High if AI outputs directly shape graded submissions
DPIA Trigger Likelihood	Low-Moderate (monitoring threshold dependent)	Moderate-High (profiling or assessment use)	Moderate (systematic sensitive data processing)	Moderate-High (integration into formal evaluation)
AI Act Risk Level (Likely)	Generally non-high risk	Potential high-risk if used in educational assessment	Context-dependent	Increased scrutiny if AI contributes to student evaluation
Required Safeguards	Transparency notice; defined retention; Article 28 contract; human escalation	Human oversight in grading; limits on profiling; assessment transparency	Strict access control; purpose limitation; sensitive data safeguards	Human supervision; clear AI-use policy; disclosure in assessed work

Governance Dimension	AI Use 1: Administrative Chatbot	AI Use 2: AI-Supported Collaboration	AI Use 3: Reflective AI Teammate	AI Use 4: LLM Co-Creation in the Virtual Phase
Controller / Processor Complexity	University controller; vendor processor; possible joint controllership	Often joint controllership between partner institutions	Elevated controller responsibility due to sensitive data	Complex vendor relationships; deployer duties under AI Act
International Transfer Risk	Medium (cloud chatbot providers)	Medium-High (collaboration tools + AI APIs)	Medium	High (LLM APIs often hosted outside EU unless institutional entity used)
Retention Sensitivity	Short onboarding period	Limited to project duration	Very limited; long-term storage should be avoided	Prompt storage should be avoided unless it is strictly necessary
Empirical Case Evidence	RWTH Aachen University chatbot data protection framing (RWTH Aachen University, 2024a)	ENHANCE BIP collaboration structures; AI-supported teamwork practices (ENHANCE Alliance, 2023)	KTH Royal Institute of Technology guidance on GenAI use in teaching (KTH Royal Institute of Technology, 2026)	Arqus Alliance BIP on science communication & generative AI (Arqus Alliance, 2025)

Source: Own elaboration

Although UNESCO (2023) does not classify AI in the same way as the four categories mentioned in this study, those practices can still be examined. Table 2 summarises how the four AI uses in BIPs align with UNESCO's regulation.

Table 2. Aligning AI in BIPs with UNESCO's AI guidance

AI Use Case	ENHANCE BIPs (2023-2026)	UNESCO Guidance (2023)
Use 1: Administrative Chatbot	AI supports logistical communication, onboarding information, and administrative guidance during the virtual phase	Data protection, transparency, and human oversight are required in AI-supported services
Use 2: AI-Supported Collaboration	AI supports group coordination, idea generation, and collaborative learning among international student teams	Ethical pedagogical use of AI and protection of collaborative and inclusive learning environments are necessary

Use 3: Reflective AI Teammate	AI supports student reflection by providing feedback and guidance during learning activities	Development of critical AI literacy and preservation of human agency in AI-mediated learning are highly recommended
Use 4: LLM- Supported Co-Creation	Generative AI supports brainstorming, drafting, and co-creation of academic outputs	Responsible use of generative AI, transparency in authorship, and validation of AI tools in education are essential

Source: Own elaboration

We can observe that the AI uses in BIPs (2023–2026) support learning and collaboration while, in line with UNESCO guidance, they require transparency, data protection, human oversight, and responsible use of generative AI.

5. Discussion of results

The first case (AI Use 1: Administrative Chatbot) focuses on chatbots for administrative orientation and onboarding in ENHANCE. RWTH Aachen University provides an example of how such services can be legally managed. Its IT Center published a data protection statement explaining that chatbot data processing is part of the university’s public service and falls under Article 6(1)(e) of the GDPR (European Data Protection Board, 2020; 2024), together with related transparency information (RWTH Aachen University, 2024a; European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2024). This approach fits the BIPs model because onboarding often involves multilingual communication, tight schedules, and repeated questions. Chatbots can provide scalable support and improve BIP mobility access. However, they must follow key GDPR principles (European Data Protection Board, 2023; 2024). Although the pedagogical role of AI in this case is indirect, onboarding chatbots can reduce administrative workload and cognitive pressure, allowing students to focus more on collaboration and intercultural exchange during the short on-site phase. At the same time, their use raises policy considerations highlighted by UNESCO (2023), particularly in the need for privacy safeguards and age-appropriate access policies. These measures help to ensure that conversational AI systems function as support tools rather than administrative decision-makers.

Another related issue appears in RWTH’s description of RWTHgpt, which presents an institutional LLM tool which stores data locally on university servers (RWTH Aachen University IT Center, n.d.). The system also restricts the reuse of chat content for external training (RWTH Aachen University, 2024b, December 11). Although RWTHgpt is not designed specifically for BIPs, it shows an example of regulation that is relevant for university alliances. In multi-institution programmes, concerns about data sovereignty increase because students come from different countries and institutions. Commercial AI services may also create uncertainty about data reuse and cross-border data processing. In this context, institutionally managed infrastructure can support innovation while still complying with GDPR requirements (European Data Protection Board, 2023, 2024). For administrative AI tools, the need for a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) depends on whether the system involves systematic monitoring, profiling, or other high-

risk processing. EU guidance explains that this threshold depends on the specific context and on the possible risks to individuals' rights and freedoms (European Commission, 2024; European Data Protection Board, 2024a). Although neither the European AI Act nor UNESCO directly regulate administrative chatbots, they emphasize on the importance of transparency and data protection when AI systems interact with users.

The second case (AI Use 2: AI-Supported Collaboration) focuses on the use of AI in challenge-based learning linked to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which is a common teaching format in BIPs (United Nations, 2015; European Commission, 2023). In this context, the value of AI is not in answering administrative questions but in supporting learning processes. AI can help students to explore ideas, to work across languages, and to collaborate more efficiently during the virtual phase. From this perspective, AI is useful when it supports higher-level thinking under human supervision. This approach is consistent with learning theories such as connectivism (Siemens, 2005) and boundary object theory (Star & Griesemer, 1989), which describe learning as a networked process supported by shared tools and resources.

In BIP mobility settings, AI can act as a shared tool that helps students from different linguistic and disciplinary backgrounds work together. However, UNESCO's human-centred approach draws attention to the aspect that authentic human interaction should remain central. AI can support collaboration through tasks (e.g. information summary, content translation, suggesting project ideas, or proofreading, etc.), however, it should not replace any social and cognitive processes that take place within student teams (Cress & Kimmerle, 2023). From a legal perspective, the AI Act (Regulation EU 2024/1689) becomes applicable when AI tools influence task assessment or course grading (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2024). Regulation classifies such educational uses of AI as high-risk and therefore requires stricter safeguards, including risk management procedures, technical documentation, transparency, and human oversight (European Union, 2024, Annex III). For this reason, more institutions are developing AI literacy frameworks and internal AI responsibility guidelines that reflect principles from international policy documents (OECD, 2023; UNESCO, 2023; European Commission, 2025; OECD, 2026).

The third case (AI Use 3: Reflective AI Teammate) involves AI assistants designed to support self-regulated learning, intercultural reflection, and learning outcomes. This role is particularly valuable in BIP mobility, where students may find it challenging to transform their experiences into learning reflections. However, such systems also raise important data protection concerns. Reflective texts may contain personal information and may reveal behavioural patterns. Under the GDPR, this may require a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), particularly when data processing poses a high risk to individuals' rights or involves systematic monitoring (European Union, 2016; European Commission, 2024). The European Data Protection Board emphasises on the importance of establishing a lawful basis when AI systems process personal data in educational contexts (European Data Protection Board, 2024b). UNESCO (2023) notes that generative AI although provides rapid feedback and suggestions for self-directed learning, it requires continuous human supervision, as AI outputs may contain inaccuracies. In learning contexts that foster critical thinking, AI can function as a cognitive partner by prompting students to reconsider arguments or to identify gaps in their reasoning. At the same time, UNESCO warns that excessive reliance on

AI may weaken the learners' ability to evaluate information independently. Therefore, AI should be used to support metacognitive awareness rather than to replace human reflection.

An important policy signal in the ENHANCE context comes from guidance by KTH Royal Institute of Technology, which states that teachers cannot require students to use generative AI tools due to unresolved legal issues, including those related to GDPR and copyright (KTH Royal Institute of Technology, 2026). It effectively sets a regulatory boundary for the use of reflective AI. Such tools may be offered as optional support, but making their use mandatory could place students in situations involving unclear data-processing conditions. Therefore, institutions should implement opt-in systems, ensure transparency, apply strict data minimisation and data retention policies, and provide human alternatives for students who prefer not to use AI-based reflection tools (European Union, 2016; European Commission, 2024).

The fourth case (AI Use 4: LLM Co-Creation in Virtual Phases) addresses LLM-enabled co-creation in the virtual phase and the broader generative turn in BIP pedagogy observed in 2025 and 2026 (OECD, 2023; UNESCO, 2023). While early BIP virtual phases were often experienced as preambles, generative AI now makes it possible to structure the virtual phase as a process of continuous work with multilingual synthesis, rapid drafting and asynchronous collaboration across time zones. This transformation is not only theoretical; it is also evidenced by documented GenAI-focused BIP activities within the European university alliance ecosystem. For example, the Arqus Alliance reported a BIP focused on science communication and generative AI, involving 22 students from three countries and designed around multilingual and multimodal narrative production (Arqus Alliance, 2025). Such programmes demonstrate how generative AI can be positioned not as a hidden productivity tool but as an object of critical practice. Students can be assessed on their ability to critique, refine, and transparently document AI-generated outputs rather than focusing on the output production alone. UNESCO (2023) also notes that AI can support creative tasks such as writing, coding, and artistic production by offering suggestions or assisting with problem-solving. Nevertheless, creative learning should remain human-centred, as excessive reliance on AI may limit the development of original thinking.

Across the four use cases analysed, a broader policy pattern emerges. UNESCO guidance suggests that institutions integrating AI into teaching and administrative practices should establish internal policies aligned with international standards. These should address data protection, risk management, AI literacy training, and human oversight. When implemented responsibly, AI can enhance learning environments; however, without such governance, institutions risk weakening both data protection and the quality of teaching and learning. At the alliance level, the ENHANCE's institutionalisation of BIPs through coordinated calls suggests that AI-related policy decisions will be made at scale (Figure 1), increasing the need for shared AI literacy frameworks (ENHANCE Alliance, 2023). In this context, not only must EU AI policies be implemented, but learners, educators, and staff must also be prepared to operate within AI-informed educational environments.

6. Conclusion

Our analysis reveals that the AI policy in ENHANCE-context mobility is best understood as an intersection of pedagogical transformation and legal governance. Administrative onboarding chatbots can be viewed as public-service infrastructure under the GDPR lawful bases, while

institutionally governed LLM services illustrate new approaches to data sovereignty and transparency. Challenge-based learning shows that AI can function as a cognitive partner that accelerates inquiry and supports multilingual collaboration, but only within the governance boundaries that preserve human oversight and avoid AI-driven evaluation roles. Reflective AI assistants display why the most pedagogically valuable uses can also be the most legally sensitive, because reflection data heightens the DPIA relevance and raises questions about voluntary participation and power asymmetry in educational contexts. Finally, the LLM-enabled reconfiguration of the virtual phase is supported by documented GenAI BIP activity in the European alliance ecosystem, and it is reinforced by policy pressures created by the AI Act's timeline, which has pushed institutions toward formalised governance and literacy frameworks.

Overall, the facts shift the view of the BIPs virtual phase from an administrative barrier to a collaborative space that shapes the success of the compressed physical mobility period. In this model, the real BIP mobility starts before travel with multilingual teamwork, and reaches its peak on-site through negotiation, prototyping, and intercultural exchange. Within the AI policy framework discussed in this study, the ongoing Blended Intensive Programme “Enhancing Sustainable Communication, Professional Competences and AI” illustrates an AI-friendly learning ecosystem. It represents collaboration among three EU technical universities (Universitat Politècnica de València, Warsaw University of Technology, and Technische Universität Berlin), the ENHANCE associate partners, and two Ukrainian Technical Universities from Kyiv and Lviv. The programme focuses on sustainability and integrates two AI uses: supported collaboration (AI Use 2) and co-creation (AI Use 4).

As ENHANCE continues to expand BIPs across different institutions, the main challenge will be to build shared AI literacy and strong data practices that protect fairness and trust. For future AI-supported BIPs, several key questions will shape how learning develops: How do legal risks differ between individual chatbot use and collaborative human-AI work? Which AI uses carry the highest risk under the AI Act? What safeguards are needed when AI is used in student assessment? By tackling these questions, the ENHANCE partnership will maintain a delicate human-AI balance in BIPs and will shape future policies.

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